

Using Integration by Parts for Fractional Calculus to Solve Some Fractional Integral Problems

Chii-Huei Yu

School of Mathematics and Statistics, Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7830903>

Published Date: 15-April-2023

Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional calculus, we solve some fractional integrals by using integration by parts for fractional calculus. A new multiplication of fractional analytic functions plays an important role in this article. In fact, our results are generalizations of traditional calculus results.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus, fractional integrals, integration by parts for fractional calculus, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The calculus founded by Newton and Leibniz is a very important scientific achievement in the history of mathematics. Fractional calculus was first proposed by the famous mathematician Hospital in 1695. A question is about what is $\frac{d^{1/2}x}{dx^{1/2}}$? After 124 years, Lacroix gave the right answer to this question for the first time that $\frac{d^{1/2}x}{dx^{1/2}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}}x^{1/2}$. However, for a long time, due to the lack of practical application, fractional calculus has not been widely used. With the development of science and technology, especially since the 20th century, the theory and application of fractional calculus began to be widely concerned. Fractional calculus has become a powerful tool to study fractional differential equations and fractional functions, and has been widely used in the research of physics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, biology, economics, and so on [1-12].

However, the definition of fractional derivative is not unique. The commonly used definitions include Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative, Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative [13-16]. Because Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative helps to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function, it is easier to use this definition to connect fractional calculus with traditional calculus.

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus, we solve the following two α -fractional integrals:

$$({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) \right], \quad (1)$$

and

$$({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[Ln_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \right] \right], \quad (2)$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Integration by parts for fractional calculus, and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions play important roles in this paper. In fact, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional calculus used in this paper and its properties.

Definition 2.1 ([17]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt. \quad (3)$$

And the Jumarie type of R-L α -fractional integral is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}I_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad (4)$$

where $\Gamma(\)$ is the gamma function.

Proposition 2.2 ([18]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x-x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (6)$$

Next, the definition of fractional analytic function is introduced.

Definition 2.3 ([19]): If x, x_0 , and a_k are real numbers for all k , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{k\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.4 ([20]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. If $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (7)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (8)$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Definition 2.5 ([21]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (11)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (12)$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (13)$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (14)$$

Definition 2.6 ([22]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha), g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ be two α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \dots \otimes_\alpha f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$. On the other hand, if $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1$, then $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the \otimes_α reciprocal of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, and is denoted by $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha -1}$.

Definition 2.7 ([23]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real variable. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (15)$$

And the α -fractional logarithmic function $Ln_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is the inverse function of $E_\alpha(x^\alpha)$.

Theorem 2.8 (integration by parts for fractional calculus) ([24]): Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, a, b are real numbers, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha), g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are α -fractional analytic functions, then

$$({}_a I_b^\alpha) [f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha ({}_a D_x^\alpha) [g_\alpha(x^\alpha)]] = [f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha)]_{x=a}^{x=b} - ({}_a I_b^\alpha) [g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha ({}_a D_x^\alpha) [f_\alpha(x^\alpha)]]. \quad (16)$$

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we solve two fractional integrals by using integration by parts for fractional calculus.

Example 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Find

$$({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) \right].$$

Solution Using integration by parts for fractional calculus yields

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) \right] \\ &= ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha ({}_0 D_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \right] \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) \right]_0^x - ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \otimes_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \right]^{\otimes_\alpha -1} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) - \frac{1}{2} ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \right]^{\otimes_\alpha -1} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) + \frac{1}{2} \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Example 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Find

$$({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[Ln_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} \right] \right].$$

Solution By integration by parts for fractional calculus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[\text{Ln}_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right] \right] \\
 &= ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[\text{Ln}_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right] \otimes_\alpha ({}_0D_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right] \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \text{Ln}_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right] \right]_0^x - ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \otimes_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha-1}} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \text{Ln}_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right] - 2 \cdot ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha-1}} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes_\alpha \text{Ln}_\alpha \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} \right] + 2 \cdot \arctan_\alpha(x^\alpha) - 2 \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha. \tag{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus, we evaluate two fractional integrals by using integration by parts for fractional calculus. A new multiplication of fractional analytic functions plays an important role in this paper. In fact, our results are generalizations of the results in classical calculus. In the future, we will continue to study the problems in engineering mathematics and fractional differential equations.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Mainardi, Fractional calculus and waves in linear viscoelasticity: an introduction to mathematical models, World Scientific, 2010.
- [2] V. E. Tarasov, Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus, Mathematics, vol. 8, no. 5, 660, 2020.
- [3] A. Carpinteri, F. Mainardi, (Eds.), Fractals and Fractional Calculus in Continuum Mechanics, Springer, Wien, 1997.
- [4] R. C. Koeller, Applications of fractional calculus to the theory of viscoelasticity, Journal of Applied Mechanics, vol. 51, no. 2, 299, 1984.
- [5] R. L. Magin, Fractional Calculus in Bioengineering, Begell House Publishers, 2006.
- [6] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering, Advanced Engineering Technology and Application, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41-45, 2016.
- [7] R. Hilfer (Ed.), Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics, WSPC, Singapore, 2000.
- [8] Teodor M. Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [9] C. -H. Yu, A new insight into fractional logistic equation, International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews, vol. 9, no. 2, pp.13-17, 2021.
- [10] C. -H. Yu, A study on fractional RLC circuit, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 3422-3425, 2020.
- [11] J. T. Machado, Fractional Calculus: Application in Modeling and Control, Springer New York, 2013.
- [12] M. Ortigueira, Fractional Calculus for Scientists and Engineers, vol. 84, Springer, 2011.
- [13] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.
- [14] S. Das, Functional Fractional Calculus, 2nd Edition, Springer-Verlag, 2011.
- [15] K. B. Oldham, J. Spanier, The Fractional Calculus; Academic Press: New York, NY, USA, 1974.

- [16] K. S. Miller, B. Ross, An Introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations; John Willy and Sons, Inc.: New York, NY, USA, 1993.
- [17] C. -H. Yu, Techniques for solving some fractional integrals, International Journal of Recent Research in Interdisciplinary Sciences, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 53-59, 2022.
- [18] U. Ghosh, S. Sengupta, S. Sarkar and S. Das, Analytic solution of linear fractional differential equation with Jumarie derivative in term of Mittag-Leffler function, American Journal of Mathematical Analysis, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 32-38, 2015.
- [19] C. -H. Yu, Study of fractional analytic functions and local fractional calculus, International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 39-46, 2021.
- [20] C. -H. Yu, Sum of some fractional analytic functions, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6-10, 2023.
- [21] C. -H. Yu, Exact solutions of some fractional power series, International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 36-40, 2023.
- [22] C. -H. Yu, Infinite series expressions for the values of some fractional analytic functions, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 80-85, 2023.
- [23] C. -H. Yu, Methods for solving some fractional integral, International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1-5, 2023.
- [24] C. -H. Yu, Some applications of integration by parts for fractional calculus, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 38-42, 2022.